

Place Modelling by Clustering Foursquare POIs in a Place2Vec-Based Approach

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Abstract. Places are geographic entities defined by specific functions with varying levels of specialization. Points of Interest (POIs) serve as proxies for these functions, with their types indicating distinct roles. This study models places by clustering Foursquare POIs based on their geographic proximity and semantic similarity, where semantic relationships are derived from the Place2Vec model, which generates POI embeddings capturing both spatial and functional contexts. The resulting place clusters are analyzed for functional diversity using entropy, revealing whether they offer specialized or multifaced experiences. This approach provides insights into the spatial-semantic structure of places and their functional complexity.

Keywords. Place Modelling, Points of Interest, Place2Vec, Clustering, Entropy

1. Introduction

Places, as human constructs, integrate geometric boundaries with experiential qualities (Tuan, 1975). POIs are geographic locations serving certain functions, and they offer a practical means to represent places. However, the dynamic nature of human activities within places often blurs their functional boundaries, making it challenge to model them solely through individual POIs. For example, a central train station may include multiple POIs such as Train Station, Cafe, Restaurant, Shop, and so on. While categorized separately, these POIs collectively form a single place identify rather than distinct entities. This highlights the importance of viewing places as aggregation of semantically and spatially related POIs.

To account for this complexity, both geographic proximity and functional relatedness should be considered in place modelling. This study aims to explore how incorporating semantic relationships between POIs influences

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the delineation and interpretation of urban places. Specifically, this study models places in Greater London in two approaches: (1) based solely on spatial distance, and (2) based on a combination of spatial and semantic distances. The resulting place clusters generated in these two approaches will be compared by examining their spatial distributions across London boroughs.

2. Methodology

2.1. Data

This study uses Foursquare POIs collected by Yang et al. (2015). The dataset uses a three-level hierarchical category structure: categories, subcategories, and sub-subcategories. For simplicity, this study focuses on the first two levels, covering 8 main categories—Food, Travel & Transport, Nightlife Spot, Outdoors & Recreation, Shop & Service, Arts & Entertainment, Professional & Other Places, and College & University—and 210 subcategories. To ensure privacy and streamline analysis, POIs in Residence category are excluded and different types of restaurants (e.g. Italian Restaurant, Fast Food) are consolidated into a single Restaurant subcategory. After preprocessing, the dataset consists of 26,840 POIs in London.

2.2. Place Modelling

Places can be conceptualized as geographic areas defined by specific functions and represented by clusters of POIs that are similar in both spatial and semantic dimensions. This study applies HDBSCAN (Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise) (McInnes et al., 2017) to identify such clusters and model them as places. Two clustering approaches are implemented. The first considers only the spatial distance between POIs, calculated as the pairwise Euclidean distance between their coordinates to reflect geographic proximity. The second approach combines spatial and semantic distances to inform the clustering process.

Semantic distance is derived from the similarity between POI subcategories, using embeddings generated by the Place2Vec model (Yan et al., 2017). Inspired by the Word2Vec model (Mikolov et al., 2013), Place2Vec captures distributional semantics in geographic space by generating embeddings based on the spatial co-occurrence of POI types. This study applies Place2Vec to generate POI subcategory embeddings and computes pairwise cosine similarities to quantify semantic relatedness. The semantic distance is then defined as $\text{semantic distance} = 1 - \text{cosine similarity}$, which is integrated with spatial distance to cluster POIs into semantically and spatially coherent places.

2.3. Place Interpretation

To examine the effect of incorporating semantic distance in place modeling, this study compares the two clustering results using Shannon's entropy of POI subcategory as an indicator. The entropy reflects the diversity of POI subcategories within each cluster. High entropy indicates that the place is multifunctional and hybrid in use, while low entropy indicates that the place is specialized in functions with only one or a few similar subcategories. For each London borough, the average place entropy is calculated and compared across the two approaches (spatial-based and combined). This comparison helps reveal how semantic information affects the functional coherence of modeled places across different parts of the city.

3. Results

HDBSCAN clustering generates 1,284 clusters and 949 clusters using the spatial-based approach and combined approach respectively. *Figure 1* and *Figure 2* show the spatial distribution of places in each approach, with colors indicating the entropy of POI subcategories within each cluster. In both approaches, places are primarily concentrated in the city center. However, the combined approach generates more compact clusters in central areas and a more even distribution in peripheral zones compared to the spatial-based approach. Notably, in the spatial-based approach, an aggregation of clusters appears in the southern part of Hillingdon Borough, around Heathrow airport, while the aggregation does not occur in the combined approach.

In terms of functionality diversity, places from the spatial-based approach tend to have higher subcategory entropy, reflecting a greater mix of POI functions. In contrast, places generated by the combined approach show lower entropy, as semantic similarity incorporated into the clustering process. *Figure 3* and *Figure 4* show the average entropy values of places in each approach across boroughs. Central boroughs tend to have low-entropy places, indicating more specialized functions and stronger spatial-semantic alignment. Peripheral boroughs often feature places with higher entropy, suggesting more multifunctional roles—though this may partly result from sparser POI distribution in certain areas.

Figure 1. Spatial Distribution of Places (Spatial-Based Approach).

Figure 2. Spatial Distribution of Places (Combined Approach).

Figure 3. Entropy Mean of Places in London Boroughs (Spatial-Based Approach).

Figure 4. Entropy Mean of Places in London Boroughs (Combined Approach).

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that clustering POIs using both spatial and semantic distances effectively models places as cohesive spatial-semantic units.

Through entropy analysis, the functional diversity of these places is investigated, distinguishing specialized areas from multifunctional ones. In London, places located in central boroughs tend to exhibit lower entropy and more focused functions, while those in peripheral areas show higher entropy, suggesting multifunctionality. This pattern, based on the analysis of Foursquare POIs, suggests that city centers often concentrate specialized economic and service functions, while peripheral zones appear more mixed-use—though this may not fully reflect on-the-ground realities. These findings offer practical implications for urban planning and smart city initiatives. Understanding the spatial-semantic structure of urban places can support better-informed decisions in zoning, infrastructure development, and public service provision.

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